

Supplemental data

Biochemical Characterization and Mutational Studies of a Novel Flap Endonuclease 1 from the Hyperthermophilic Euryarchaeon *Thermococcus barophilus* Ch5

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Supplementary Table S1. Sequences of the oligonucleotides used in this work

Number	Length (nt)	Sequence (5'-3')
1	45	Cy3-CGAACTGCCTGGAATCCTGACGAC <u>A</u> TGTAGCGA ACGATCACCTCA
2	45	TGAGGTGATCGTTCGCTACATGTCGTCAGGATTCCAG GCAGTTCG
3	19	AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
4	24	AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
5	45	TTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTT <u>T</u> IGTCGTCAGGATTCCAGG CAGTTCG
6	45	TGAGGTGATCGTTCGCTACATTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTT TTTTTTT
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Supplementary Table S2. DNA substrates prepared with the oligonucleotides in

Table S1

DNA substrate	Combination
ssDNA	1
dsDNA	1 + 2
5'-flap DNA	1 + 4 + 6
3'-flap DNA	1 + 3 + 5
5'-splayed DNA	1 + 6
3'-splayed DNA	1 + 5

B

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Figure S1. Kinetic analysis of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1 at 25°C. One hundred nanomolars 5'-flap DNA was used as the substrate to determine the Tb-FEN1 activity in the presence of 1000 nM enzyme at 45°C for various times (2 - 90 min) at 25°C. A. The DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. B. Determination of the reaction rate of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. The amount of remaining substrate was plotted as a function of time by the single exponential decay equation to yield the k_{endo} value. CK: the DNA cleavage reaction without the enzyme.

Figure S2. Kinetic analysis of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1 at 30°C. One hundred nanomolars 5'-flap DNA was used as the substrate to determine the Tb-FEN1 activity in the presence of 1000 nM enzyme at 45°C for various times (2 - 60 min) at 30°C. A. The DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. B. Determination of the reaction rate of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. The amount of remaining substrate was plotted as a function of time by the single exponential decay equation to yield the k_{endo} value. CK: the DNA cleavage reaction without the enzyme.

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Figure S3. Kinetic analysis of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1 at 35°C. One hundred nanomolars 5'-flap DNA was used as the substrate to determine the Tb-FEN1 activity in the presence of 1000 nM enzyme at 45°C for various times (1 - 60 min) at 35°C. A. The DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. B. Determination of the reaction rate of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. The amount of remaining substrate was plotted as a function of time by the single exponential decay equation to yield the k_{endo} value. CK: the DNA cleavage reaction without the enzyme.

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Figure S4. Kinetic analysis of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1 at 40°C. One hundred nanomolars 5'-flap DNA was used as the substrate to determine the Tb-FEN1 activity in the presence of 1000 nM enzyme at 45°C for various times (40 s - 40 min) at 40°C. A. The DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. B. Determination of the reaction rate of DNA cleavage by Tb-FEN1. The amount of remaining substrate was plotted as a function of time by the single exponential decay equation to yield the k_{endo} value. CK: the DNA cleavage reaction without the enzyme.

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